

Analysis and Comparison of Three Alternate Direct Liquid Cooling Concepts for Segmented Axial Flux Machines

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Abstract—Effective thermal management systems (TMS) are essential for achieving high current and power densities in electric machines. This study presents a comparative evaluation of three direct liquid cooling (DLC) strategies for a yokeless and segmented armature (YASA) axial flux machine (AFM): a flooded stator (FS), an end-winding jet (EWJ) system, and modular encased segments (MES). Using steady-state thermal simulations, the configurations are assessed in terms of heat transfer, required pumping power, and temperature uniformity. Results highlight key trade-offs between performance and design complexity, with the MES configuration demonstrating superior thermal efficiency, requiring 39% less flow than the FS and 60% less than the EWJ.

Index Terms—Thermal analysis, direct liquid cooling, axial flux machines

I. INTRODUCTION

The push toward electrification has driven rapid advancements in electric machine (EM) technology, particularly in sectors like transportation that demand high power densities, compact form factors, high efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

One response to these demands is the yokeless and segmented armature (YASA) machine [1], a type of axial flux machine (AFM) characterized by its modular and piecewise stator topology. This configuration introduces significant benefits such as compact shape and high torque density, but also unique thermal, mechanical, and electromagnetic challenges.

This paper investigates three direct liquid cooling (DLC) strategies tailored for YASA AFMs. Each configuration is evaluated through computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations, focusing on temperature control, required pumping power, and system complexity. The aim is to inform early-stage design decisions that enable higher current and power densities through selecting the optimum thermal management system (TMS).

This research has received funding from the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program EU MSCA DN under grant agreement no. 101072580, HIPO: *Integrated high-speed power systems for industry and mobile applications*. The content of this publication does not reflect the official opinion of the EU. Responsibility for the information and views expressed in the publication lies entirely with the authors.

II. CONTEXTUAL REVIEW FOR COOLING SYSTEM DESIGN

This section highlights key thermal management strategies relevant to the development of a large YASA AFM for electric mobility. The configurations discussed here do not represent an exhaustive list; for a more comprehensive review of AFM TMS, see [2]. Instead, the focus is on geometric constraints and design opportunities in prior work that directly inform the analysis in the following sections.

A key challenge in cooling YASA stators lies in their geometry. Unlike radial flux machines, which typically allow access to both end windings and the stator circumference to be used as cooling surfaces, a single stator, double rotor AFM such as the YASA exposes only the outer end winding region. The disk faces are adjacent to the air gaps, and the inner windings face inwards.

Despite the geometric constraints, a valuable opportunity presents itself through the modular, segmented stator design, which allows for increasing the spacing between segments to accommodate integrated cooling features such as heat fins, pipes, or embedded channels [3]–[9].

Direct liquid cooling (DLC) via immersion cooling, i.e. filling the machine’s void volumes with coolant, is particularly notable. As shown in [3], this idea has, since the inception of the YASA topology, been viewed as an important feature of the design. However, simply flooding the void volume does not ensure an equal distribution of cooling fluid to each part, and thus, hotspots may form. To address this, several studies introduce flow-directing elements to improve coolant routing and thermal uniformity [4], [5], [8].

In [7], a TMS is proposed where cooling volumes around individual segments are connected in parallel via an external manifold. This compartmentalized design ensures more uniform fluid delivery and temperature regulation. Notably, this system uses impinging jets to enhance local heat transfer, an approach that may also be adapted to augment flooded stator designs, further explored in the end-winding jet configuration in Section III-B.

TABLE I
ELECTROMAGNETIC PARAMETERS OF THE MACHINE

Parameter/metric	Value
Max power / torque	125 kW / 875 Nm
Slot / pole combination	24 / 20
DC bus voltage / phase current	800 V / 90 A
Stator outer diameter (active)	450 mm
Stator body axial length (excl. tooth tip)	36 mm

III. MACHINE CASE STUDY

The three TMS evaluated in this study are based on a common machine geometry and operating specification. The AFM under development is intended for use as a low-speed, high-torque drive unit in a heavy-duty transport vehicle. Its initial sizing and design basis are described in [10].

A. Axial Flux Machine Geometry

The electromagnetic and mechanical aspects of the machine are being developed in parallel, allowing early-stage integration of TMS features into the design. While this co-design process enhances flexibility, it also means certain machine details, such as a complete efficiency map, are not yet finalized, limiting the analysis of TMS performance across the full operating envelope.

At this stage, however, high-fidelity detail is not essential. The objective is to comparatively evaluate the cooling system architectures under consistent geometric and operating conditions. While some variation in both machine performance and thermal behavior may arise between this early analysis and the final prototype, the comparative trends across TMS configurations are expected to remain valid.

Table I summarizes the primary electromagnetic and geometric parameters used in the comparison study. These parameters are held constant across all simulations.

B. Thermal Management System Configurations

Based on the design considerations reviewed in Section II, three DLC TMS configurations are selected for comparative evaluation. All variants use oil to directly cool the copper-wound stator segments via one or more enclosed chambers in close proximity to the primary heat sources.

The main distinction between the TMS lies in the routing and distribution of coolant within the stator. The three architectures are defined as follows:

- A flow chamber enclosing all segments, with a large internal flow path and a single inlet and outlet (Fig. 1(a)).
- Multiple jets directed at the outer end-winding region, with a common collection sump at the base (Fig. 1(b)).
- Individually encased segments, each with configurable inlet and outlet ports for parallel or serial flow (Fig. 1(c)).

The configurations are illustrated in Fig. 1 and discussed in further detail below.

Fig. 1. YASA DLC TMS concept alternatives under consideration
Flow volume in cyan, arrows indicate flow inlet/outlet

a) *Flooded Stator (FS)*: This configuration serves as the baseline, reflecting the original TMS concept developed for the YASA machine. It requires minimal modification to the stator aside from sealing a common flow volume. With a single inlet and outlet, the internal flow path would seem straightforward. However, ensuring uniform coolant distribution across segments is challenging due to multiple parallel flow paths and possible geometric inconsistencies introduced during assembly. Additionally, its single-pass layout leads to a progressive increase in coolant temperature along the flow direction, increasing segment-to-segment temperature variation. Prior studies have demonstrated that targeted flow control features are critical for improving the FS configuration's thermal performance [4], [5].

In this study, a simplified version of the flooded stator concept, comparable to the baseline presented in [4], is modeled and evaluated.

b) *End Winding Jets (EWJ)*: This configuration combines the ideas from [3] and [7], exploiting the high local heat transfer coefficient provided by impinging jets while benefiting from the lower pressure loss from an open flow volume. Coolant is introduced radially through slot gaps above each stator segment and exits via a sump located at the machine base. The number of jets, N_j , is determined by the number of stator segments, N_s , minus the segments reserved for the outlet sump, N_o , such that $N_j = N_s - N_o$. Properly balancing these parameters is critical: misconfiguration can cause uneven flow distribution and hotspots, similar to those observed in unregulated immersion cooling.

Due to the multiple inlets, a manifold is required to distribute fluid evenly among the jets. For this study, the inlet pressures are assumed equal across all slots, yielding uniform flow. While this layout offers potentially improved internal fluid distribution compared to the FS, its increased complexity in terms of jet count and manifold design may raise costs and assembly effort.

A notable advantage of both the EWJ and FS configurations is the ability to enclose ancillary wiring such as phase connectors or the neutral point within the same flow volume. For instance, these components could be housed at the machine's inner radius, expanding the casing inwards as needed. Although promising for integration, such design elements fall outside the scope of the simplified analysis presented here.

Sealing the stator remains a key challenge. One solution, applied in commercial YASA designs, is the use of axial bulkhead disks. While this ensures the seal, it increases the air gap, adversely impacting electromagnetic performance. An alternative is to machine holes through the disks, preserving the air gap but increasing leakage risk and potential windage losses. These trade-offs are visualized in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Axial bulkhead - increased air gap length or potential leakage path

c) *Modular Encased Segments (MES)*: In this configuration, each stator segment is housed within its own fluid-tight enclosure, assembled prior to integration. Inspired by the concept in [7], the MES approach provides several advantages:

- Controlled and predictable internal flow paths
- Enhanced sealing reliability due to smaller fluid volumes
- Capability for individual leakage testing prior to assembly
- Flexible configuration of parallel or serial connections

While the first three points are more qualitative in nature, the configurability of the flow network stands out as a key strength and will be investigated later. As shown in Fig. 1(c), segment pairs are connected at the inner radius, while the outer interfaces can be configured as inlets, outlets, or pass-throughs depending on the desired hydraulic arrangement. This modularity enables custom flow paths that can be optimized to meet specific thermal or system-level requirements.

Nevertheless, this approach comes with trade-offs. The individualized casings increase design complexity and manufacturing cost, and the architecture makes it challenging to integrate cooling for phase connectors or the neutral point.

In summary, the three configurations represent a spectrum of trade-offs between thermal performance, mechanical complexity, and integration constraints. While the latter aspects will not be further elaborated in this study, the comparative analysis in subsequent sections evaluates their cooling performance to inform design selection.

IV. COMPARISON METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the effectiveness of the three TMS configurations, three key performance indicators (KPIs) are used: the heat transfer coefficient, h , the required fluid pumping power, \dot{W}_p , and the temperature variation across the stator, σ_T . These

metrics capture thermal efficiency, hydraulic cost, and cooling uniformity, respectively.

Each quantity depends on system-level parameters including the inlet temperature T_F , volumetric flow rate \dot{V} , heat generation from machine losses \dot{Q}_L , and the EM and TMS geometry.

The heat transfer coefficient is derived using a rearranged form of Newton's law of cooling:

$$h = \frac{\dot{Q}_L}{A(T_{\text{Surf}} - T_F)} = \frac{\dot{q}_{\text{Cu}}V_{\text{Cu}} + \dot{q}_{\text{Fe}}V_{\text{Fe}}}{A(T_{\text{Surf}} - T_F)} \quad (1)$$

Here, A is the surface area for heat exchange, T_{Surf} is the average stator surface temperature. The heat loss may also be described by the volumetric heat generation times the volume, $\dot{q}V$, of the stator copper and iron parts (Cu and Fe, respectively).

The required pumping power is calculated as:

$$\dot{W}_p = \frac{\dot{V}\Delta p}{\eta_p} \quad (2)$$

where Δp is the pressure drop across the TMS and η_p is the assumed pump efficiency, fixed at 75%.

Temperature uniformity is assessed by the standard deviation of the average segment temperatures:

$$\sigma_T = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{Se}}} (\bar{T}_i - \bar{T}_{\text{Se}})^2}{N_{\text{Se}}}} \quad (3)$$

with \bar{T}_i being the average temperature of segment i and \bar{T}_{Se} the mean across all N_{Se} segments.

CFD simulations were carried out using 2D, steady-state, laminar models focused exclusively on the TMS domain. The simulation depth equals the axial stator body length in Table I. Automatic transmission fluid (ATF) is used as the coolant, modeled with temperature-dependent properties from [11]. Table II summarizes the key simulation parameters.

All simulations were performed in ANSYS Fluent, with post-processing of performance metrics handled in MATLAB.

TABLE II
THERMAL ANALYSIS PARAMETERS

Parameter/metric	Value
Volumetric flow rate (range)	[3 - 18] L/min
Inlet temperature (constant)	60 °C
Maximum winding temperature	190 °C
Heat generation rate (winding / core)	3.7 mW/mm ³ / 0.73 mW/mm ³

V. RESULTS

The TMS comparison results are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Fig. 3 plots the evaluated KPIs as functions of flow rate, while Fig. 4 illustrates the average temperature for each stator segment. The segments are labeled 1 to 24, arranged clockwise starting from the one o'clock position. Table III summarizes the minimum flow rate required to keep winding temperatures below 190 °C and lists the corresponding KPI values.

TABLE III
TMS ANALYSIS KPIS

Type	\dot{V}_{\min} L/min	h W/m ² K	\dot{W}_p W	σ_T °C
FS	7.5	533	5.39	16.1
EWJ	11.4	262	0.147	4.61
MES	4.6	338	2.14	11.2

A noteworthy, albeit counterintuitive, observation is that the EWJ and MES systems outperform the FS design in terms of lower pumping power and temperature variation, despite consistently exhibiting lower average heat transfer coefficients, h , as seen in Table III and Fig. 3(b).

This is due to differences in how flow is distributed. In the EWJ and MES configurations, the total volumetric flow rate is divided across multiple parallel channels or inlets, reducing the local flow rate per segment. This leads to lower local velocities and, by extension, lower local convective heat transfer coefficients. The FS, in contrast, routes the entire flow through a single shared volume, resulting in higher local velocities and a higher overall h value.

However, this apparent advantage is offset by drawbacks such as increased residence time and poor fluid distribution past the separate segments of the stator. These effects lead to greater segment-to-segment temperature variation. In fact, a combination of high h and high σ_T may indicate the presence of recirculation zones and localized hotspots, rather than superior thermal performance.

A. Flooded Stator

Coolant enters between segments 24 and 1 and exits between segments 23 and 24. The resulting temperature distribution, shown in Fig. 4(a) reveals a rising trend from 1 to 24, driven by the progressive heating of the coolant. Additionally, significant segment-to-segment variation is observed, which remains largely unchanged as the flow rate increases. This is confirmed in Fig. 3(d), where σ_T decreases with increasing \dot{V} , but the effect plateaus beyond approximately 9 L/min.

This performance limitation stems from uneven coolant distribution due to the shared flow volume. Increasing flow rate alone does not resolve this imbalance. As discussed above, mitigating this issue would require internal structures to redirect the flow, but this has not been implemented here.

B. End Winding Jets

In this setup, $N_j = 16$ jets are used, with ATF entering through slot openings above the top two-thirds of the machine, segments 1–8 and 17–24, and exiting through a collection volume spanning segments 9–16. This configuration creates two symmetrical cooling zones: segments 1–12 and 13–24.

Fig. 3(d) shows the advantage of distributed flow in reducing σ_T compared to the FS, demonstrating a consistent and significant improvement of uniformity across the flow range. The increased flow rate in the outlet sump also compensates for the coolant heating, resulting in mostly uniform temperature throughout the stator.

(a) Maximum copper temperature

(b) Heat transfer coefficient

(c) Pump work

(d) Temperature variation

Fig. 3. Comparison of variation of KPIS with increasing flow rate

(a) Flooded Stator

(b) End Winding Jets

(c) Modular Encased Segments

Fig. 4. Maximum copper temperature distribution for each TMS variant

However, as shown in Fig. 4(b), a hotspot develops at segments 9 and 16. These areas receive limited coolant because the final jet upstream is diverted directly into the outlet volume, bypassing the channels between segments 8–9 and 16–17. This is a geometric limitation of the current design which could be mitigated by adjusting N_j or, once more, incorporating flow-blocking features.

Due to the locally low heat transfer coefficient and the presence of the hotspot, a relatively high flow rate is required to keep the system within thermal limits. Nevertheless, as shown in Fig. 3(c), the EWJ configuration requires the lowest pumping power among the three systems. With improved design to mitigate bypass, the EWJ could present a highly competitive cooling solution. However, the practical complexity of implementing such refinements, including jet alignment and sealing, may limit its feasibility in real-world applications.

C. Modular Encased Segments

The baseline structure of the MES employs one inlet and one outlet, with the internal fluid volumes connected in two parallel series. The inlet and outlet are located opposite each other between segments 24–1 and 12–13, respectively, resulting in a symmetrical layout, similar to the EWJ configuration.

In this arrangement, the temperature distribution, shown in Fig. 4(c), increases toward the outlet section due to the progressive heating of the coolant. Since the flow is restricted to a confined volume, there are limited temperature variations due to flow imbalance. Instead, increasing the flow rate flattens the temperature profile by reducing the coolant’s temperature rise along the flow path. This also implies that at sufficiently high \dot{V} , the fluid does not heat significantly and thus σ_T may even reach zero, as seen in Fig. 3(d).

This advantage comes at the cost of higher pressure loss: the MES exhibits the highest pressure drop among the three systems, as can be observed in Fig 3(c). Nevertheless, its superior flow control allows effective cooling at a lower volumetric flow rate than the alternatives, leading to a lower minimum required pumping power compared to the FS system.

Due to its modular construction, the MES can be reconfigured with multiple inlets and outlets to further enhance performance. Fig. 5 and Table IV compare performance for configurations with one, two, and three inlet/outlet pairs.

As shown in Table IV, increasing the number of inlets reduces the average heat transfer coefficient due to lower local velocities but significantly improves temperature uniformity

(a) Maximum copper temperature

(b) Pump work

Fig. 5. Comparison of MES TMS KPIs with multiple inlets/outlets

TABLE IV
MES KPIS VARYING NO. OF INLETS

Type	\dot{V}_{\min} L/min	h W/m ² K	\dot{W}_P W	σ_T °C
1 Inlet	4.6	338	2.14	11.2
2 Inlets	6.1	296	0.814	7.86
3 Inlets	7.4	274	0.495	6.05

and reduces pumping power. This is attributed to smaller fluid temperature gradients between the inlet and outlet. Notably, tripling the number of flow paths results in a 77% reduction in \dot{W}_P and a 46% reduction in σ_T .

Although the MES does not outperform the EWJ, it offers marked improvements over the FS and provides valuable flow control flexibility worth further exploration.

VI. CONCLUSION & FURTHER WORK

This paper presents a comparative thermal analysis of three direct liquid cooling (DLC) thermal management systems (TMS) for a segmented axial flux machine (AFM): a flooded stator (FS), an end-winding jet (EWJ) configuration, and a modular encased segment (MES) design.

The study demonstrates that configurations with multiple inlets and distributed flow paths, such as EWJ and MES, achieve significantly lower pressure losses (97% and 60%, resp.) and temperature variation (71% and 30%, resp.) compared to the FS, despite exhibiting lower average heat transfer coefficients.

While the performance trends are clear, several practical considerations remain for future work. For FS and EWJ systems, adding flow-blocking features may improve thermal uniformity and should be included in future simulations to enable more balanced comparisons. Additionally, the benefit of cooling the winding interconnections, possible in FS and EWJ, is not captured in the current 2D model; a 3D extension may be necessary to accurately assess this effect.

The assumption of laminar flow should also be verified, as turbulence would affect both flow distribution and heat transfer, requiring appropriate adjustments to the model.

Although distributed flow paths enhance cooling performance, this study does not address the external distribution infrastructure. Practical implementation requires manifolds and parallel piping to maintain balanced flow, which may introduce additional design complexity and cost. These factors must be considered in subsequent development phases.

Despite these limitations, the study offers early-stage insight into DLC strategies for AFMs and provides a foundation for informed TMS selection and refinement. Based on the findings, the MES configuration emerges as the most promising due to its strong thermal performance and modular design flexibility.

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